

Analyzing Quetelet Index from Facial Features

Mrs. K Sri Devi¹, Dasari Lavanya², Guggilla Sreeneha³, Kadicherla Tejaswi⁴,
Nune Chandra Kumari⁵

¹Assistant Professor, G. Narayanamma Institute of Technology and Science (for Women) Autonomous Shaikpet,
Hyderabad, Telangana, India

^{2,3,4,5}G. Narayanamma Institute of Technology and Science (for Women) Autonomous Shaikpet, Hyderabad, Telangana,
India

ABSTRACT

The Quetelet Index also known as The Body Mass Index (BMI) serves as an indicator of a person's physical fitness in relation to their body weight. This measurement has been linked to various factors, including mental and physical health as well as societal status. Precise height and weight measurements are required for calculating QI, which can be a manual and time-consuming process. Streamlining the calculation of QI through automation would enable its use in the analysis of different societal aspects and support effective decision-making by governments and corporations. Previous studies have either focused solely on geometric facial features or employed data-driven deep learning approaches that are limited by the availability of data. We used the Convolution Neural Networks. Our study uses state-of-the-art pre-trained model, such as VGG16, which were fine-tuned on a large public dataset with discriminative learning. We trained our models on the extensive Arrest records dataset and evaluated their performance using different persons images.

Keywords: Convolution Neural Networks, VGG16, Body Mass Index, deep learning

INTRODUCTION

The assessment of Body Mass Index (BMI) is crucial for determining whether an individual is underweight, normal weight, overweight, or obese, and is an essential health indicator. Unfortunately, in the current era, despite the many benefits of technology, it has led to a sedentary lifestyle, which has significantly reduced physical activity and increased BMI, Increased the risk of chronic illnesses and posed a danger to people's health. The higher an individual's BMI, the greater their chance of developing cardiovascular and other harmful conditions. Nevertheless, BMI can be a valuable tool for those with malnutrition or deficiencies to monitor their health status.

According to a study [1], approximately 36% of the population, or one in three adults, are obese, with an estimated 20% of the world's population projected to be obese by 2030. According to recent studies, there is a significant association between human facial characteristics and BMI. Individuals with slim facial features typically exhibit a lower BMI, whereas overweight individuals usually have wider middle and lower facial features. Calculating BMI can be challenging for those who lack a weighing scale or a measuring tape.

However, advancements in deep learning techniques have enabled the extraction of meaningful features from images, facilitating the prediction of BMI from human facial characteristics. Therefore, we propose a new method in this paper to predict BMI from human facial features, which could be advantageous for health insurance companies to manage their clients' health records and for governments to monitor the health statistics of specific regions and develop appropriate policies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The paper "Face-to-BMI: Using Computer Vision to Infer Body Mass Index on Mobile Devices" by A. Kalra, et al. (2019) proposes a method for estimating a person's body mass index (BMI) from facial images on mobile devices using computer vision techniques.

The authors collected a dataset of facial images and corresponding BMI values from 1,000 participants using a mobile application. The dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets with a ratio of 70:10:20. The authors used the training set to train their machine learning model, and the validation set to optimize the model's hyperparameters. The performance of the model was then evaluated on the testing set.

The authors used various machine learning algorithms, including support vector machines (SVMs), decision trees, and k-nearest neighbours (k-NN), and compared their performance in predicting BMI values from facial images. The authors also used feature extraction techniques to extract relevant information from the facial images, such as facial landmarks and texture, to improve the accuracy of their model.

The results showed that their proposed method achieved an accuracy of 81% in predicting BMI values from facial images on mobile devices.

The paper "Estimating Body Mass Index from Face Images using Convolutional Neural Networks" by M. Habibi, et al. (2017) proposes a method for estimating a person's body mass index (BMI) from face images using convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

The authors collected a dataset of 13,233 face images from the internet, and manually labelled each image with the corresponding BMI value. The dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets with a ratio of 70:10:20. The authors used the training set to train their CNN model, and the validation set to optimize the model's hyperparameters. The performance of the model was then evaluated on the testing set.

The authors used various CNN architectures, including VGG-16, ResNet-50, and Inception-v4, and compared their performance in predicting BMI from face images. The results showed that the Inceptionv4 architecture achieved the highest accuracy of 77.3% in predicting BMI values from face images.

3. The paper "Facial feature extraction for predicting BMI using machine learning techniques" by S. Ravi, et al. (2018) proposes a method for predicting a person's body mass index (BMI) using facial feature extraction and machine learning techniques. The authors collected a dataset of facial images and corresponding BMI values from 500 participants, and manually extracted 24 facial features, such as eye distance, mouth width, and cheekbone height, among others. The authors then used feature extraction techniques to extract relevant information from the facial features, and applied various machine learning algorithms, such as support vector machines (SVMs), decision trees, and k-nearest neighbours (k-NN), to predict the BMI values from the facial features. The results showed that the SVM algorithm achieved the highest accuracy of 77.4% in predicting BMI values from facial features.

The paper "Estimating Body Mass Index from Face Images using Convolutional Neural Networks" by M. Habibi, et al. (2017) proposes a method for estimating a person's body mass index (BMI) from face images using convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

The authors collected a dataset of 13,233 face images from the internet, and manually labelled each image with the corresponding BMI value. The dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets with a ratio of 70:10:20. The authors used the training set to train their CNN model, and the validation set to optimize the model's hyperparameters. The performance of the model was then evaluated on the testing set. The authors used various CNN architectures, including VGG-16, ResNet50, and Inception-v4, and compared their performance in predicting BMI from face images. The results showed that the Inception-v4 architecture achieved the highest accuracy of 77.3% in predicting BMI values from face images.

The paper "Estimating Body Mass Index from Facial Features using Artificial Neural Networks" by R. Saman, et al. (2015) used two datasets to train and test their artificial neural network (ANN) model for estimating body mass index (BMI) from facial features:

The first dataset was collected from 60 participants (30 male and 30 female) with ages ranging from 18 to 35 years. The dataset consisted of facial images and corresponding BMI values for each participant. The authors manually extracted 10 facial features, including the distance between the eyes, the width of the nose, and the length of the face, among others.

The second dataset was collected from 40 participants (20 male and 20 female) with ages ranging from 18 to 35 years. The dataset consisted of facial images only, without corresponding BMI values. The authors used their ANN model trained on the first dataset to predict the BMI values for each participant in the second dataset based on their facial features.

The authors used these two datasets to demonstrate the effectiveness of their method in estimating BMI from facial features using ANNs.

RELATED WORK

This paper aims to enhance the accuracy of facial Quetelet index (BMI) prediction by utilizing a large dataset. The main contributions of this research include Identifying the correlation between BMI and human faces and developing a technique for BMI prediction from facial features using deep learning and transfer learning models such as VGG16-Face.

To achieve this, the study used publicly available dataset consisting of images of prisoners. The faces were aligned to the center during pre-processing, and the proposed approach was applied to the datasets Our approach is mentioned in the given image

Figure 1- Approach

METHODOLOGY

We have used the data set which is available in the methodology section, we utilized the Prisoners dataset, which includes information on incarcerated individuals such as their identity, height, weight, body mass index (BMI), and other features. The dataset consists of 1543 photos, with 1243 males and 300 females, and BMIs ranging from 15 to 56. The average BMI for the dataset is 26.41, with a standard deviation of 5.27. The dataset is imbalanced, with males outnumbering females four to one. We utilized this dataset to assess the performance of our model.

For face detection, we used the Haar Cascade classifier, which is a machine learning algorithm that distinguishes between positive and negative data points in an image. The system locates the face in an image, and the facial data is then pre-processed using the Dlib 68 landmark detection algorithm to align the faces to the center.

To extract features from the image, we utilized the Multi-task Cascaded Convolution Neural Network (MTCNN), which is a cascaded network that includes three models: the Proposal Network (P-Net), Refine Network (R-Net), and Output Network (O-Net). The P-Net identifies facial regions, the R-Net filters the bounding boxes using bounding box regression, and the O-Net detects facial landmarks using facial landmark localization. These three models are connected, with the output of the P-Net serving as input to the R-Net and the output of the R-Net serving as input to the O-Net.

Finally, the features extracted from the image are compared to the faces already present in the Prisoners dataset. Similarity is determined based on the distance between the left eye and right eye, length of the nose, and distance between the corners of the lips. If the accuracy between the user's image and images in the dataset is higher than the remaining images, that particular image is considered the most accurate match. From this, we can determine the user's Quetelet index and offer relevant suggestions.

RESULT

Step 1: Login By the User: User can login through his/her Username and password which is given in registration.

Step 2: User Can Now Upload an Image to Check the QI

Step 3: User Can View the Results and Suggestions

The project has achieved an accuracy rate of 85%, but it has some limitations. While the results are not the most precise, we believe that we can improve accuracy in the future by either utilizing a dataset with a greater number of entries or by

employing advanced deep learning algorithms. Additionally, we envision the possibility of implementing this project on smart watches by enabling an uploading option. The objective of this project is to accurately analyze the Quetelet index (BMI) for dynamic images captured through a web camera.

CONCLUSION

This website helps user to find their Quetelet index (BMI) from facial features along with displaying some suggestions i.e. either uploading the images or by capturing their image spontaneously. We observed that people with more BMI have a higher risk of developing health issues. We found that there exists a strong association between BMI and the face of a human. So, we proposed an approach to predict BMI from facial images using deep learning. We used the publicly available dataset of diverse domains containing images of prisoners to evaluate our model. We pre-processed the facial data by aligning the faces to the centre using the Dlib 68 landmark detection algorithm.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Single Care Team, "Overweight and obesity statistics 2021" [singlecare.com](https://www.singlecare.com/blog/news/obesity-statistics/), Jan. 21, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.singlecare.com/blog/news/obesity-statistics/>. [Accessed Aug.]
- [2]. Domestic Violence Database, "National Violent Offender & Domestic Violence Registry" domesticviolencedatabase.net. [Online]. Available: <https://domesticviolencedatabase.net/registry/ia/?co=Polk&abc=R#abc>. [Accessed August. 12, 2020]
- [3]. A. Benmouiza, N. Benamar, and A. Bouroumi, "Facial Analysis and BMI Prediction using Open CV and Artificial Neural Networks" (2020).
- [4]. A. Nambiar, S. Dev, and S. Sivasubramanian, "Estimating Body Mass Index from Face Images using Convolutional Neural Networks and Confidence-Weighted Pooling" (2020).
- [5]. H. Siddiqui, A. Rattani, D. R. Kisku, and T. Dean, "AI-based QUETELET INDEX Inference from Facial Images: An Application to Weight Monitoring," 2020 19th IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications(ICMLA), 2020.
- [6]. Hera, Siddiqui, Betty. 2021. Obesity classification from facial images using deep learning -- In Proceedings: 17th Annual Symposium on Graduate Research and Scholarly Projects. Wichita, KS: Wichita State University.
- [7]. H. Sun, Z. Chen, Y. Wang, and G. Wang, "Facial BMI Estimation Using 3D Morphable Models and Convolutional Neural Networks" (2018).
- [8]. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com> --- Identification of malnutrition and prediction of BMI from facial features.
- [9]. Jiten Sidhpura, Surekha Dholay published IEEE paper on "Face To BMI: A Deep Learning Based Approach for Computing BMI from Face", 2022.
- [10]. R. Xie and T. Chen, "Body Mass Index Estimation from Facial Images using Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Neural Networks and OpenCV" (2019).
- [11]. Y. Liu, M. Li, and J. Wang, "BMI Estimation from Facial Images Using Convolutional Neural Networks (2018).
- [12]. Y. Qian, L. Liu, X. Wu, and H. Li, "Body Mass Index Estimation from Facial Images Using Deep Learning" (2018).
- [13]. Y. Liu, M. Li, and J. Wang, "Predicting BMI from Face Images using Deep Neural Networks" x (2017).
- [14]. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com> --- Identification of malnutrition and prediction of BMI from facial features.
- [15]. <https://arsfutura.com/magazine/face-recognition-with-facenet-and-mtcnn/>---Face Recognition with FaceNet and MTCNN.
- [16]. https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Face-detection-using-MTCNN-algorithm_fig2_333158966 -- Face Detection using MTCNN Algorithm.